

Appendix B: Figures of pole directions and shapes for individual asteroids

Fig. B.1. Same as Fig. 2, but for the asteroid (5189) 1990 UQ.

Fig. B.2. Same as Fig. 3, but for the asteroid (5189) 1990 UQ.

Fig. B.3. Same as Fig. 2, but for the asteroid (6569) Ondaatje.

Fig. B.4. Same as Fig. 3, but for the asteroid (6569) Ondaatje.

Fig. B.5. Same as Fig. 2, but for the asteroid (8566) 1996 EN.

Fig. B.6. Same as Fig. 3, but for the asteroid (8566) 1996 EN.

Fig. B.7. Same as Fig. 2, but shown in the all-sky projection and for asteroid (66251) 1999 GJ₂.

Fig. B.8. Same as Fig. 2, but for the asteroid (86450) 2000 CK₃₃.

Fig. B.9. Same as Fig. 3, but for the asteroid (86450) 2000 CK₃₃.

Fig. B.10. Same as Fig. 2, but in the a projection of the northern ecliptic hemisphere for asteroid the (98943) 2001 CC₂₁.

Fig. B.11. Same as Fig. 3, but for the asteroid (98943) 2001 CC₂₁.

Fig. B.12. Same as Fig. 2, but for the asteroid (137199) 1999 KX₄

Fig. B.13. Same as Fig. 3, but for asteroid (137199) 1999 KX₄.

Fig. B.14. Same as Fig. 2, but shown in the all-sky projection and for asteroid (276786) 2004 KD₁.

Fig. B.15. Same as Fig. 3, but for asteroid (276786) 2004 KD₁. The shape of the global best-fit solution ($P_{\text{sid}} = 5.01863$ h) is shown in the top row, while the shape for another possible period $P_{\text{sid}} = 5.017051$ h is shown in the bottom row.

Fig. B.16. Same as Fig. 2, but in the a projection of the northern ecliptic hemisphere for asteroid the (495615) 2015 PQ₂₉₁.

Fig. B.20. Same as Fig. 2, but shown in the all-sky projection and for asteroid (22099) 2000 EX₁₀₆.

Fig. B.17. Same as Fig. B.2, but for asteroid (495615) 2004 KD₁. The shape of the global best-fit solution ($P_{\text{sid}} = 13.7413$ h) is shown in the top row, while the shape for another possible period $P_{\text{sid}} = 13.7518$ h is shown in the bottom row.

Fig. B.18. Same as Fig. 2, but for asteroid (512245) 2016 AU₈.

Fig. B.19. Same as Fig. 3, but for asteroid (512245) 2016 AU₈.